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Context in research on teaching quality: bringing a complex idea into the spotlight

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes how teaching effectiveness research deals with context when investigating teaching quality. It examines three categories of variables that are often treated as context: classroom composition, content, and country. An in-depth analysis of the literature on teaching quality where these variables are treated as context suggests that context can have an effect on the empirical findings of teaching-quality research and that this could be an explanation for why results are often inconsistent. Analyzing the explicit and implicit conceptual assumptions about the relation between context and teaching quality in empirical studies revealed that classroom composition and content are often not considered essential to teaching quality, and that it is generally assumed that measures of teaching quality are internationally valid. The paper ends by discussing how future studies might approach the issue of context so that consistency in research on teaching quality is improved.

KEYWORDS

Teaching quality; teaching effectiveness; context; generalizability; generalization

Introduction

Researchers have been studying teaching quality and its effect on students for decades. Because of the inherent complexity of teaching, most empirical studies of teaching quality have had a narrow focus on selected aspects of teaching. For example, studies have examined how different dimensions of teaching quality affect student achievement and interest when teaching the Pythagorean theorem (Lipowsky et al., 2009), how teaching quality differs when the same teacher teaches in different classrooms (Cherng et al., 2022), and how teaching differs between countries (Stigler & Hiebert, 1999). Each of these papers focused on some aspects of teaching quality and relegated others not relevant to the key research questions to the background. In

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teaching effectiveness research (TER), these background characteristics are usually referred to as *context*. The contexts of studies can vary as can the extent to which each study takes context into account. In this paper, we take a close look at these differences and investigate how studies approach context and the extent to which context is related to teaching quality. We examine these questions by using three key categories of context which together constitute much of the contextual variation: classroom composition, teaching content, and country (i.e., the educational system in which teaching is embedded). We conduct an in-depth analysis of how these context variables influence selected study results and then discuss how future studies might approach the issue of context to capture teaching quality more adequately.

The relevance of (ignoring) context in research on teaching quality

In TER, teaching quality is primarily interpreted as focusing on the effectiveness of teaching, thus on teaching that is positively related to student outcomes (see Charalambous et al., 2025, this special issue). Many articles explicitly or implicitly equate teaching with teacher behavior and attributes. The equivalence has been repeatedly critiqued over the past few years. Studies have highlighted that teaching is more than teacher behavior and encompasses interactions between teachers, students, and content, all embedded in an environment¹ (D. K. Cohen et al., 2003). Further, researchers (e.g., Gitomer & Bell, 2013) have underscored that it is important to make a clear distinction between teaching quality and teacher quality. The former focuses on what happens between teachers and students in relation to the content, whereas the latter focuses on teacher characteristics such as their knowledge or motivation (Fauth et al., 2019).

Conducting empirical studies of teaching quality is challenging because the “embeddedness of educational phenomena in social life ... results in the myriad of interactions that complicate our science” (Berliner, 2002, pp. 19–20). Quantitative studies in TER generally deal with the issue of complexity by focusing on selected aspects of teaching and learning and relegating others to the background as context (J. Cohen et al., 2018; Grossman & Stodolsky, 1995) in order to generalize across these specifics. Accordingly, conceptualizations and measures of teaching quality have been applied in a wide range of contexts, and the relationships between teaching and learning have often been treated as if they are universal (Vieluf & Klieme, 2023). This is also apparent in meta-analyses, which require generalizations in order to draw meaningful conclusions (Renkl, 2022), as well as in parts of initial and further teacher training where the idea is widespread that teachers and teacher educators can be given general guidance that can improve teaching quality in any setting.

At the same time, this approach is only meaningful if the assumption holds that the results of these studies can be generalized beyond the specific context in which they were originally investigated (Luoto, 2023). Evidence suggests, however, that this type of generalization is often problematic. There are significant differences in the results of studies looking at similar issues (Shavelson & Dempsey-Atwood, 1976; Vieluf & Klieme, 2023), and the generalizations regularly go beyond the scope of the existing evidence (Biddle & Anderson, 1986). In this article, we argue that while it is expedient to simplify a complex topic in order to identify patterns or key issues, dismissing context has resulted in small effects and inconsistent results. In order to develop a better, more inclusive,

concept of teaching quality, we need to look carefully at class composition, content, and country, variables which have hitherto been virtually dismissed as *context*.

Conceptualizations of context in TER

In TER, context is a poorly defined umbrella term that can encompass a wide variety of characteristics (Biddle & Anderson, 1986; Creemers & Scheerens, 1994; Dunkin & Biddle, 1974). For example, in an edited book on theorizing teaching (Praetorius & Charalambous, 2023a) well-known authors from TER and related fields reflected on teaching and its quality. In this book, which provides an up-to-date overview of TER and related fields, the authors used the term context, or variations thereof, such as contextual variables or contextual conditions, 205 times, usually without defining or explaining it. Contributing authors thus assumed that teaching is influenced by diverse contextual variables (see Appendix 1 for a classification of the uses of the word in the book) ranging from student characteristics such as age, socioeconomic, and previous knowledge, to teacher characteristics such as teaching experience, knowledge, and motivation, to regional and national characteristics such as curriculum, resources invested in education, and the amount of teaching students experience. Interestingly, the very same variables are deemed to be of key importance in one place and context in another, mostly visible for content or subject (Charalambous & Praetorius, 2023; Hiebert & Stigler, 2023; Hill & Lampert, 2023; Kyriakides et al., 2023; Schoenfeld, 2023; Vieluf & Klieme, 2023) but in one instance also for student age group (Kyriakides et al., 2023). The fact that, for example, even within chapters content is sometimes treated as context but also distinguished from it (e.g., by referring to “content and context”) suggests that there is no established definition of context in TER.

We believe that one of the main reasons for the heterogeneous treatment of context in this field is the complexity of teaching quality as a concept. Context usually refers to something external to the unit of analysis. In other research areas, this unit is often the individual (e.g., in organizational research; see Mowday & Sutton, 1993). We would argue that in TER some researchers are following a similar logic, having in mind the actions of an individual (i.e., the teacher) in a context (i.e., everything else), whereas others are interpreting the unit of analysis to be a social system (e.g., D. K. Cohen et al., 2003).

The present paper

This paper aims to explore how the term context is used in TER and the extent to which it is related to teaching quality in selected empirical studies. As one of the core assumptions of TER is that findings on teaching quality can be generalized regardless of context, we first provide a narrative literature review of the relationship between teaching quality and context:

- (1) What is the relationship between the selected context categories and teaching quality?

As context covers numerous variables which cannot be summarized in a single paper, we decided to focus this review on three categories of context: classroom

composition, content, and country. These categories were selected because they are often labeled as context in the literature and encompass a wide spectrum of context variables.

In order to establish the boundaries between teaching quality and context in a systematic way, we then summarize the assumptions about the relationship between context and teaching quality found in each of the selected studies. This leads to our second research question:

- (2) What are the explicit and implicit conceptual assumptions of the relationships between context and teaching quality that underlie the empirical studies?

After discussing the three context categories with respect to the research questions, we make suggestions for how to improve the way context is treated in future teaching-quality research, aiming for more consistent results and, perhaps, even larger effect sizes.

Method

Literature search

The focus of the paper was to investigate how the three categories of context, classroom composition, content, and country, are treated in TER studies. Although a structured literature search methodology was used, this study is not a thorough systematic literature review. That would have required systematic protocols and screening procedures, a second coder, and an appraisal of the studies using a quality checklist (Siddaway et al., 2019). We opted for a leaner approach because (a) the research questions did not warrant such an exhaustive approach and (b) conducting parallel systematic reviews for three context categories would not have been feasible and too much to report in a single paper.

We assembled a group of researchers who each had specialized knowledge of at least one of the selected categories: classroom composition, content, and country. Their knowledge of the literature therefore provided a reasonable basis for this paper. To enhance this literature body, a literature search was conducted for each of the categories in spring 2024 using EBSCO (ERIC), Web of Science, Scopus, and Google scholar.

The following search terms were used for all three categories: “teaching quality” OR “instructional quality” OR “teaching practices” OR “instructional practices” OR “teaching effectiveness”. For classroom composition, the following additional terms were used: “student body” OR “classroom composition” OR “student composition”. For content, the additional search terms were “content,” “subject-specific,” “domain-specific,” “subject-specificity,” and “domain-specificity”. For countries, the additional terms were: “across context*” OR “cultural context*” OR “educational system” OR “cross-cultural comparison*”.

The results were further screened to ensure that the papers were peer-reviewed, focused on research on years K–12 (i.e., primary and secondary education), published in English or German, and focused on teaching quality in relation to one of the context categories. We used the snowballing technique to find further studies. This process identified 18 to 22 papers for each category (for a list of all papers, see [Appendix 2](#)).

Study type classification

The context categories were treated very differently by the studies, so we classified the selected papers into three types on the basis of their methodological approach. Type 1 studies compared aspects of teaching quality in terms of the selected context category, without taking into account student outcomes. These included, for example, mean comparisons or measurement invariance of teaching quality between entities in a category and comparisons of conceptualizations of teaching quality between entities in a category. Type 2 were mediation studies focused on the relation between teaching quality and student outcomes, with the context category as the independent variable. Type 3 were moderation studies focusing on the relation between teaching quality and student outcomes with the context category as moderator as well as multigroup comparisons where the relations between teaching quality and student outcomes were compared across a context category.

Presentation of research findings

Our purpose was to explore the role of context in TER and whether context might help explain small effect sizes and inconsistent findings. In order to understand how the selected studies treated context, we described the sample, dimensions of teaching quality studied, types of data generated, context-related findings, as well as strengths and limitations (see [Tables 1–3](#)). We decided not to present all of the studies identified by the search because it would have been too much to report on in a single paper. Instead, we present illustrative examples from each context category, choosing one or more examples of each of study types 1–3 described above. This resulted in four or five methodologically sound studies per context category. The selection was somewhat arbitrary; however, we checked that our conclusions would not have been altered had we selected a different set of studies by reviewing the remaining papers, although this is not reported here.

As each context category is a separate topic, we decided to diverge from the usual structure of an empirical paper. There is a section for each category with a definition and an explanation of its significance, the results of the literature review, and a short discussion. The last section summarizes the results across the three categories and discusses them.

Classroom composition as context

Definition and importance of classroom composition effects

Student experiences of the learning environment, and therefore also their achievement outcomes, are greatly influenced by the other students in the same classroom. This was one of the fundamental insights of an influential study by Coleman et al. (1966), which showed that the social composition of a school affects student achievement. Despite its methodological limitations, the Coleman study prompted multiple disciplines, such as educational sciences, sociology, psychology, and economics, to address these so-called composition effects. These effects refer to the impact of class-aggregated student characteristics on individual learning outcomes, over and above personal student

Table 1. Illustrative examples of the identified studies on the role of classroom composition for teaching quality.

Study	Sample	Dimensions of teaching quality	Types of data	Study type	Findings with respect to context	Strengths and limitations with respect to context
Fauth, Wagner, et al. (2020)	<p>Study 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Germany - Various subjects - 174 teachers, 106 classes, 3,408 students (no student background data) <p>Study 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Germany - History - 1 teacher, 30 classes, 769 students - 14.5 years old 	Clarity, emotional support, discipline	Student and observer ratings	1	<p>Study 2: A large proportion of the variance in student ratings of teaching quality is between classes for one teacher</p> <p>Study 3: In observer ratings, some aspects of teaching quality are more affected by classroom composition (discipline) than others (clarity and support)</p>	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>Within-teacher, between-classroom design allows for estimation of variations of the same teacher in different classrooms</p> <p>Limitations:</p> <p>No randomized assignment of teachers to classes</p>
Cherng et al. (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - United States - Various subjects - 2,515 teachers 	Overall scores of FFT (Danielson, 2013) and CLASS (Pianta & Hamre, 2009)	Observer ratings and VAM	1	There is considerable within-teacher, across-classroom variation in teaching quality in all dependent variables (FFT, CLASS, VAM); this variation is linked to the racial composition of the class	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>Large database, randomized assignment of teachers to classes within randomization blocks</p> <p>Limitations:</p> <p>Only overall scores of teaching-quality measures are reported</p>
Rjosk et al. (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Germany - German and English as a foreign language - 352 classes, 8,047 students - approximately 15 years old 	Focus on language, student-oriented climate, and classroom management	Student ratings	2	All dimensions of teaching quality were associated with classroom composition; only focus on language predicted reading achievement; teachers of classes with students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds taught less demanding language lessons, which was in turn associated with their students having lower attainment	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>Rich database and sophisticated study design for mediation analyses</p> <p>Limitations:</p> <p>Teachers and classes are confounded</p>

(Continued)

Table 1. Continued.

Study	Sample	Dimensions of teaching quality	Types of data	Study type	Findings with respect to context	Strengths and limitations with respect to context
Göllner et al. (2020)	- Germany - Math - 259 classes, 2,508 students - approximately 15 years old	Disturbances, monitoring (both aspects of classroom management)	Student ratings	2	The achievement distribution of students in a classroom predicted aspects of classroom management (i.e., aspects of student behavior); only these student-related aspects significantly predicted subsequent student achievement; teacher monitoring was unaffected from composition	Strengths: Thorough distinction between different aspects of classroom management (student or teacher related) Limitations: Teachers and classes are confounded; only student ratings as measures of teaching quality
Decristan et al. (2017)	- Germany - Science - 1,070 students, 54 teachers, 54 classes - Age 8.8	Cognitive activation, supportive climate, classroom management	Student ratings	3	The effects of teaching quality are not independent from classroom composition; effects of all three dimensions on student learning were more pronounced in classrooms with a more heterogeneous classroom composition	Strengths: Innovative operationalization of context (classroom heterogeneity) Limitations: Cross-sectional study design

Note: FFT = Framework for Teaching; CLASS = Classroom Assessment Scoring System; VAM = value-added models.

characteristics at the individual level (Harker & Tymms, 2004; van Ewijk & Sleegers, 2010; Zimmer & Toma, 2000). This has been widely discussed as an important factor influencing student achievement (van Ewijk & Sleegers, 2010) and motivation (Fleischmann et al., 2022).

Although empirical studies have shown that the composition of the classroom may lead to different learning conditions and thus influence student performance (Driessen, 2002; Goldsmith, 2011; Opdenakker & Van Damme, 2013), researchers have not paid much attention to the mechanisms behind this relationship. It is interesting to note that in the sociological literature one of the most frequently discussed key mechanisms driving composition effects is teaching quality (Dreeben & Barr, 1988; Harker & Tymms, 2004; Harris, 2010; Wilkinson et al., 2000). In these studies, teaching quality is seen as a mediator that helps to explain why students perform better in classrooms with a more favorable student composition. This is an unfamiliar perspective for TER, as researchers in this field have a working assumption that teaching quality is an important lever for improving student achievement and that teaching quality mainly depends on the quality of teachers.

From the perspective of research on teacher evaluation, teaching quality represents the target construct and classroom composition is context. In this field, the link between classroom composition and observational measures of teaching quality can be problematic because such correlations may lead to unfair evaluations of a teacher's performance (Cherng et al., 2022). This is important because many teacher evaluation systems include classroom observations or student ratings of teaching quality to estimate *teacher* quality (Campbell & Ronfeldt, 2018; Cherng et al., 2022; see also below). The composition and behavior in a classroom may also explain inconsistent findings in TER. If teaching quality is strongly dependent on classroom composition but, for example, student behavior in the classroom is ignored by empirical studies, the effects of teaching quality may be underestimated or even overestimated.

Results reported by the identified studies

A review of empirical research in TER shows that the different perspectives described above also reflect different conceptual assumptions about the relationship between context and teaching quality: Is classroom composition important for teaching quality? What are the assumptions on which the empirical studies are based? An overview of the selected studies discussed in this section is provided in [Table 1](#).

Type 1 studies

Our literature search revealed that there are numerous studies that report correlations between class- or school-aggregated student characteristics (sociocultural, cognitive, and motivational, e.g., Buell et al., 2017; Fauth et al., 2021; Hachfeld & Lazarides, 2021) and teaching quality. These studies show, for example, that classroom management seems to be easier with more motivated students (Fauth et al., 2021). They are, however, generally unable to distinguish whether classroom composition, different teaching styles, or another factor contributed to the differences in the teaching-quality ratings. The non-random allocation of teachers to classes can also affect

correlations as a more favorable student composition attracts more competent teachers (Rice, 2010; See et al., 2020).

In a rather unusual research design, Fauth, Wagner, et al. (2020) examined the teaching-quality ratings by students and external observers of one teacher who taught the same content in 30 different classes. The results showed that the ratings of teaching quality were remarkably varied and that teaching quality was associated with the motivational and cognitive composition of the students in the classes. The authors also examined the teaching-quality ratings of 95 teachers, each rated by two different classes (Fauth, Wagner, et al., 2020; see also Gaertner & Brunner, 2018, and Lei et al., 2018, for a similar approach). These results showed that over half of the variance that would have been attributable to the teacher in a two-level model was actually attributable to teacher–student interactions (i.e., classroom level, nested within teachers).

That the teaching quality of the same teacher differs substantially depending on the class being taught is confirmed by several studies from the Measures of Effective Teaching (MET) project. Cherng and colleagues (2022) investigated whether classroom-to-classroom variation in teaching quality was “due to differences among teachers, as opposed to differences among classrooms taught by the same teacher” (p. 179). They demonstrated that half of the total classroom variance in teaching-quality measurements exists within teachers between classes (Cherng et al., 2022, p. 185; see also Campbell & Ronfeldt, 2018, and Steinberg & Garrett, 2016, for similar findings drawing on the MET randomized teacher sample; Kane et al., 2013) and show that these differences are associated with classroom student demographics. Interestingly, the authors found similar effects when they looked at teachers’ value-added scores instead of teaching-quality ratings.

In summary, the studies we reviewed showed that the measured teaching quality of a teacher appears to be affected by classroom composition. With reference to Research Question 1, classroom composition, and accordingly also student behavior, is important for teaching quality.

Type 2 studies

Because the concept of teaching quality being a mediator between student composition and student outcomes is not very widespread in TER, there are few mediation models in empirical studies. A study by Rjosk et al. (2014) found that teachers of classes with students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds provided them with less challenging learning opportunities, which was in turn associated with their students having lower attainment (see also Rjosk et al., 2015, and Wenger et al., 2020, for a similar approach). Göllner and colleagues (2020) were able to show that the achievement distribution of students in a classroom predicted aspects of classroom management (i.e., aspects of student behavior; see Fauth, Wagner, et al., 2020). Interestingly, only student-related aspects significantly predicted subsequent student achievement, whereas aspects related to teacher behavior did not. Thus, if the measure of classroom management only captured teacher behavior, effects would be systematically lower. This can help to explain inconsistent findings in TER as teaching quality is not operationalized in a consistent manner between empirical studies. Studies variously use items that focus on student behavior, or those that focus on teacher behavior, or have items where it is unclear whose behavior is being referred to (Fauth, Göllner, et al., 2020; Vieluf & Klieme, 2023). With reference to Research Question 1, these studies show that classroom composition is important not

only for teaching quality but also for student outcomes. With reference to Research Question 2, it is important to note that the underlying assumptions of these studies contradict the usual approach in TER. Here, teaching quality is not viewed as an indicator of teacher quality. Instead, teaching quality is merely a mediator: The teaching quality a teacher is able to deliver is largely determined by the “quality” of the students in the classroom.

Type 3 studies

Studies in this group suggest that some teaching practices might have a different effect on different students. Researchers have proposed, for example, that less able students might need more structure and support than more able ones (Hamre & Pianta, 2005). Likewise, Decristan and colleagues (2017) investigated whether the effect of teaching quality would differ depending on the heterogeneity of students in a classroom. They found several interactions indicating that the link between teaching quality and student achievement was more pronounced in classrooms with a more heterogeneous classroom composition. Again, inconsistent findings in TER can arise when researchers consider or neglect such interaction effects. With reference to Research Question 2, Type 3 studies make assumptions that differ from those of Type 2 studies. Treating teaching quality as a moderator implies that teaching quality remains consistent and is independent from the students that are being taught. Type 2 studies would, for example, state that cognitive activation is higher in classrooms with a more favorable student composition. Type 3 studies would, by contrast, say that the same level of cognitive activation in a certain classroom would lead to different learning outcomes for different students that depend on their individual backgrounds.

Content as context

Definition and importance of content effects

The category of content is relevant for TER on multiple levels. First, this category refers to subjects which each present learners with subject-specific types of content, meaning that effective teaching in mathematics will likely differ in some respects from effective teaching in religious education or arts. Second, teaching may be more or less effective in different content areas *within* subjects, such as interpreting a piece of literature versus studying spelling rules in students’ school language (Keller et al., 2024). We use the term content in the following in order to capture both the specific content and the broader subject, because we consider both relevant for TER in general and research on teaching quality in particular (Mayer, 2004; Reusser & Pauli, 2021). However, our review of the literature indicates that most studies consider *subjects* without explicitly discussing what content was taught in the observed classrooms.

Within subject-specific teaching research, content is generally viewed as an important, possibly defining, characteristic of teaching quality: If the teaching is not adapted to reflect the demands of the content, how are students going to understand it (Rothgangel et al., 2020)? By contrast, studies in TER often treat content as a context variable. These studies either evaluate teaching quality across a range of content areas (Klieme, 2006) or seek to uncover cognitive or motivational aspects of learning which

transcend content areas and represent universals of teaching and learning (e.g., Dietrich et al., 2015).

Some aspects of teaching quality are of common interest for subject-specific and generic research. For example, aspects of cognitive activation are fundamental for high-quality teaching in both. However, there are areas, such as accuracy of content, which are covered only in subject-specific approaches (Praetorius & Charalambous, 2018).

Results of the studies identified

In our overview of research on content, we have included subject-specific and generic studies. An overview of the studies discussed in this section is provided in Table 2. The studies are Type 1 (i.e., studies exploring measures of teaching quality in various subjects) or Type 3 (i.e., studies exploring the effects of teaching quality on student outcomes in various subjects). We could not identify any Type 2 studies.

Type 1 studies

The research questions posed by Type 1 studies, which compare aspects of teaching quality across content areas, are exemplified by the title of a study by J. Cohen et al. (2018), “Does Teaching Quality Cross Subjects?” As the authors observe, “evaluation systems treat measures of teaching as measures of teachers without recognizing the ways in which instructional quality may vary across subjects” (J. Cohen et al., 2018, p. 1). In terms of the instructional triangle, Type 1 studies explore “whether shifting the content corner of the instructional triangle is associated with observable changes in teaching quality” (J. Cohen et al., 2018, p. 2). To investigate this empirically, J. Cohen et al. used data from two teaching-quality observation systems (Tripod and the Class Assessment Scoring System [CLASS]) to establish the relationship between teaching quality in two different subjects, mathematics and English language. They found that dimensions assessing the affective and organizational atmosphere of the classroom were quite consistent across subjects. However, cross-content correlations were much lower for dimensions measuring instructional support (e.g., content understanding and instructional dialogue). Given the consistently low correlations for these features across different observational tools, the authors concluded that “classrooms may be different places with distinct features depending on the content of the instruction” (J. Cohen et al., 2018, p. 11).

The idea that content directly influences teaching is also suggested in a study by Fitzgerald and Palincsar (2019), which explored how teachers engage students in academic sensemaking in different subjects (mathematics, science, history, and literature). In a review design, the authors investigated “the practices in which teachers engage when the purpose is to position students as sensemakers” (p. 227). By combining and comparing different studies from these subjects, they concluded that teacher practices of sense-making are domain specific in nature, and that investigating the respective differences is a productive lens for teaching-quality research.

With reference to Research Question 1, studies classified as Type 1 thus make the case for content to be considered as highly relevant for teaching quality (e.g., J. Cohen et al., 2018; Fitzgerald & Palincsar, 2019; Praetorius et al., 2016; Scherer &

Table 2. Illustrative examples of the identified studies on the role of content for teaching quality.

Study	Sample	Dimensions of teaching quality	Types of data	Study type	Findings with respect to context	Strengths and limitations with respect to context
J. Cohen et al. (2018)	- United States - Mathematics and English - 572 classrooms - 11,674 students - Grades 4–5	Between three (CLASS, 10 items) and seven dimensions (Tripod, 36 items); e.g., positive climate, teacher sensitivity, behavior management	Student and observer ratings	1	Cross-content correlations were lower for instructional support, and higher for emotional support and classroom organization	Strengths: Within-classroom cross-subject design (i.e., the same classrooms in both subjects), two different measures Limitations: Subjects limited to English and mathematics
Fitzgerald & Palincsar (2019)	Conceptual review	Student engagement in sensemaking	Literature study	1	Teacher sensemaking practices are domain specific in nature (case studies)	Strengths: Sensemaking is established as a lens for examining subject-specific and overarching aspects of teaching quality Limitations: Concept of sensemaking refers to different aspects of teaching quality which are difficult to untangle
Jaekel et al. (2021)	- Germany - Mathematics and German - 401 classrooms - 6,479 students - Grades 5–10	Classroom management, supportive climate, cognitive activation (16 subdimensions, 61 items in total)	Student ratings, students' grades	1	Correlations between subjects are moderately negative (e.g., clarity, challenging tasks), moderately positive (e.g., structuredness, feedback) or not significant	Strengths: Large sample, measures capture many facets of teaching quality Limitations: Focused on mathematics and German; tests of student achievement (predictor) not tailored to curricular learning goals
Dietrich et al. (2015)	- Germany - Mathematics and German - 60 classrooms - 1,155 students - <i>M</i> age 10.59	Teacher support (five items)	Student ratings and self-reports of intrinsic value and effort	3	Similar effects of teacher support on intrinsic value and effort across subjects	Strengths: First study to examine cross-subject contrast effects of teacher support Limitations: Students were new to teachers, so assessment of their support contained "a fair amount of students' projections" (p. 52)

(Continued)

Table 2. Continued.

Study	Sample	Dimensions of teaching quality	Types of data	Study type	Findings with respect to context	Strengths and limitations with respect to context
Flunger et al. (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Netherlands - Mathematics and German - Nine classrooms - 202 students - <i>M</i> age 13.80 	Autonomy-supportive strategies (providing choices, rationales, accepting frustration, and stimulating interests)	Student and teacher ratings, student self-reports of motivation and engagement	3	No substantial domain dependency in the associations between autonomy support and the outcomes was found	<p>Strengths: Intensive repeated measurement design with a pre-test in two domains</p> <p>Limitations: Limited sample size and generalizability (i.e., Dutch eighth and ninth graders in the academic track), 3 weeks of lessons out of a whole school year</p>

Note: CLASS = Classroom Assessment Scoring System.

Gustafsson, 2015). They reveal distinct techniques of sensemaking that are intricately tied to specific content areas (Fitzgerald & Palincsar 2019), or low correlations of the same feature of teaching quality across different domains of instructional content (J. Cohen et al., 2018). In summary, these studies show that teaching quality is not a uniform concept across content areas. At the same time, further investigation of the precise degree to which teaching quality is associated with content is needed, especially since this variation may stem from using different frameworks, measurement instruments, and perspectives.

Type 3 studies

Type 3 studies focus on the relationship between teaching quality and student outcomes with content as moderator. The study by Dietrich et al. (2015) is a typical example. The study used dimensional comparison theory to investigate the effect of teacher support in mathematics and German on the development of students' effort and intrinsic value. It also investigated how the classroom environment in one subject could have an effect on students' intrinsic value and effort in another. It found that higher levels of teacher support in German were negatively related to intrinsic value and effort in mathematics. On the basis of these results, the authors suggest that students' classroom experiences in all subject areas should be considered holistically. The study, however, did not include any content-specific aspects of teaching quality.

The study also reveals some of the common (implicit) conceptual assumptions about the relationship between content and teaching quality that underpin TER (Research Question 2): In studies that aim to investigate mechanisms of teaching quality that can be generalized across multiple subjects, content is often classified as context. In fact, studies have shown that aspects such as autonomy support (Flunger et al., 2022) or teacher support (Dietrich et al. 2015) are associated with positive student outcomes in a variety of contexts, meaning that content serves as a context variable in these studies. However, these studies are not aligned with subject-specific aspects of teaching quality and are therefore more distal to the outcomes being investigated, making it more likely that the influence of teaching on student outcomes is underestimated.

Country as context

Definition and importance of country effects

When country is context in teaching-quality studies, it usually means that samples come from different nation states. It is generally convenient to use the term *country*, which is also often used to designate a specific culture and society (Brown & Schweisfurth, [in press](#)). However, cultures and languages often transcend borders, and some countries are much more socially, ethnically, and linguistically homogeneous than others (Fischer et al., 2019). Some countries have decentralized systems with several different co-existing educational systems while others are more centralized. In other words, when researchers investigate teaching quality in different countries, there is an assumption that *country* is a meaningful and homogeneous contextual entity that may explain what happens in schools or in education at large. This has been called methodological nationalism (Sobe, 2016). Although this assumption is overly simplistic, it is still worth investigating

similarities and differences in teaching between countries as it can “make the familiar strange” by illuminating prevalent teaching practices in our own countries (Alexander et al., 2000) and highlight how teaching is shaped by factors such as country-specific policies, material conditions, as well as cultural practices and beliefs (Paine et al., 2016).

Results of the studies identified

TER focusing on differences between countries usually treats countries as context, and it is important to consider how it is used, what assumptions this usage reflects, and what the empirical findings are, to further explore the usefulness of country as context. Because collecting data from multiple countries is costly, international studies of teaching quality are mostly based on international large-scale assessment data from student or teacher questionnaires and, to a lesser extent, classroom observations.

There are studies that collapse multiple countries into one data set and do not treat country as context. They are based on the (implicit and strong) assumption that some countries are so similar that the country does not have to be considered. Examples are the Pythagoras Study (Lipowsky et al., 2009) that uses data from German and Swiss German classrooms and a video study of Norwegian and Swedish language arts classrooms (Tengberg et al., 2022). However, in most cases, teaching-quality studies that include different countries treat country as context and have research questions targeting similarities and differences between countries. These are the studies on which we focus our review. The identified studies (see Table 3) are either Type 1 (examining teaching quality in different countries without outcome measures), or Type 3 studies (correlating patterns of teaching quality with student outcomes across countries). No Type 2 studies (treating teaching as a mediator between country and learning outcomes) were identified.

Type 1 studies

Type 1 studies often present or compare characteristics and/or the frequency of teaching practices and teaching quality (on a quality scale) between different countries. While these studies do not measure effects of teaching quality, they can provide some insight into the consistency of results across countries. One example of a cross-cultural study of effective teaching practices is Grant et al. (2013), a study that used observations, interviews, and artifacts to examine teaching practices, teaching quality, and the professional thinking of award-winning teachers in the United States and China. The researchers found that excellent teachers in these countries show both similarities (e.g., a variety of teaching activities across different levels of cognitive activation) and differences (e.g., type and frequency of activities such as lecturing and technology use). The *country* context in such studies tends to be at the forefront of any interpretation of findings. For example, Grant and colleagues stress that the differences in practice and beliefs identified can be traced to cultural values (such as Confucian heritage, nurture versus nature), national curricula, collaborative traditions, and structural differences between the education systems. Other Type 1 observation studies (e.g., the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study [TIMSS] video studies, Hiebert et al., 2003; Stigler & Hiebert, 1999) also describe both differences and similarities of teaching patterns across countries and suggest that teaching is a cultural activity (Stigler & Hiebert, 2018).

Table 3. Illustrative examples of the identified studies on the role of country for teaching quality.

Study	Sample	Dimensions of teaching quality	Types of data	Study type	Findings with respect to context	Strengths and limitations with respect to context
Grant et al. (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - USA and China - Variety of subjects - $N = 16 + 16$ classrooms - Age not specified (elementary and secondary teachers) 	<p>Stronge's (2007) teacher effectiveness framework:</p> <p>Prerequisites of teaching, teacher as a person, classroom management, planning for instruction, implementing instruction, assessing student progress</p>	Classroom observations, teacher interviews, and artifacts	1	<p>There are similarities and differences in quality teaching practice</p> <p>Similarities: (a) using a variety of instructional strategies to encourage student involvement in activities and lessons, (b) planning yet remaining flexible and spontaneous, (c) understanding students' learning, (d) thinking about and reflecting on teaching, (e) monitoring and assessing student progress, and (e) creating a positive classroom learning climate</p> <p>Differences:</p> <p>Chinese teachers anticipated students' misconceptions during the planning process, faced more challenges with differentiation and authentic learning experiences; US teachers experienced more autonomy in planning, provided more opportunities for student-centered learning opportunities, and incorporated assessment of student learning in planning and instruction</p>	<p>Limitations:</p> <p>Small sample, descriptive, phenomenological study of effective teachers in their own contexts, not related to outcome measures</p>
Fischer et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Macao, Shanghai, Taipei, Ireland, England, Scotland, Belgium, France, Switzerland, Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Chile, Colombia, Mexico - Mathematics - 1,000 students per country 	Classroom management (five items); student support (five items), cognitive activation (nine items)	PISA 2012 student ratings	1	Limited measurement invariance across linguistically diverse countries; level of comparability varies across dimensions, items, and linguistic clusters.	<p>Limitations:</p> <p>Cross-sectional data, and individual-level data (not possible to aggregate to class level due to the PISA design)</p>

	- 15-year-old students					
Bellens et al. (2019)	- Flanders (Belgium), Germany, and Norway - Grade 4 - Math and science - Around 13,500 students, around 730 classrooms	Classroom management (five items); supportive climate (five items); cognitive activation (seven items)	TIMSS 2015 student ratings	3	Significant positive relationships between classroom management and achievement in two countries; significant positive relationships for supportive climate and achievement in one country; no positive relationship for cognitive activation and achievement for any of the countries, significant negative relationship for Flanders	Limitations: In some countries some items were deleted for reasons of model convergence; cross-sectional study; descriptive comparison rather than statistical testing of differences as only partial measurement invariance could be established in previous studies using the same data
OECD (2020)	- Chile, Colombia, England, Germany, Japan, Spain, Mexico, and Shanghai - Mathematics (quadratic equations) - 50–100 teachers per country - Grade 8 or 9 (except Chile: Grade 11)	Classroom management (three components); social-emotional support (two components); quality of subject matter (two components); quality of instruction (nine components)	TALIS video observations	3	Teaching practices were significantly associated with test scores only in Colombia after accounting for students' background and their prior mathematical knowledge; teaching quality is related to levels in initial student test scores in some countries; some teaching-quality dimensions were related to interest and self-efficacy in some countries	Limitations: No measurement invariance analyses reported Strengths: Longitudinal design, accounting for student pre-knowledge
Herbert et al. (2022)	- Colombia, England, Germany, Japan, Mexico, Shanghai - Mathematics (quadratic equations) - 50–100 teachers per country - Grade 8 or 9 (except Chile: Grade 11)	Classroom management (disruptions; three items); teacher support for learning (three items); cognitive activation (four items); student participation in discourse (three items)	TALIS video student ratings	3	All teaching-quality dimensions reached metric invariance, yet in some countries only partial; no scalar invariance for any dimensions, thus no mean comparisons across countries possible; only few teaching-quality dimensions were related to achievement gains, interest, and self-efficacy, and also only in very few countries, if any	Strengths: Tested for measurement invariance; longitudinal design

Note: PISA = Programme for International Student Assessment; TIMSS = Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study; TALIS video = Teaching and Learning International Survey video study.

Another category of Type 1 study focuses explicitly on comparing measurement metrics across countries. An example is Fischer et al. (2019), which examined the measurement invariance of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2012 student questionnaires on teaching quality in mathematics. Like other similar studies, they found that the comparability of teaching-quality measures between linguistically diverse countries was limited and that the level of comparability varies across dimensions of teaching quality. The results suggest that country means cannot be compared and that the variation in respondents' cultures can lead to culturally specific interpretations of constructs.

Taken together, Type 1 studies signal that there are similarities and differences in teaching practices across countries, which suggests that country (as a proxy for language and culture) is an important factor in teaching quality (Research Question 1). Any comparison of teaching quality requires measurement-invariance analyses to confirm cross-cultural validity, and the teaching constructs selected as well as the measures used affect the level of measurement invariance.

Type 3 studies

Nearly all of the Type 3 studies examining relationships between teaching and student outcomes across countries are based on international large-scale assessment student survey data. The teaching-quality conceptualizations in these studies are mostly based on research from Western countries (Caro et al., 2016; Eriksson et al., 2019). The studies also often have a cross-sectional design, which means that they cannot uncover any causal or longitudinal effects (Carnoy et al., 2016). Bellens et al. (2019), for example, used TIMSS 2015 data and reported that the cross-sectional relationships between teaching quality and student achievement vary between dimensions of teaching quality and between the three countries being studied, with classroom management showing a positive relationship in two out of three countries, supportive climate showing a positive relationship in one country, and cognitive activation showing a negative relationship.

The Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) video study, with its longitudinal design, is an exception. This study focused exclusively on quadratic equations in mathematics lessons. It used observation as well as student surveys to measure the effects of teaching quality on achievement, interest, and self-efficacy across eight (Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development [OECD], 2020) and six (Herbert et al., 2022) countries. These two publications, one focusing on observations (OECD, 2020) and one on student surveys (Herbert et al., 2022), found inconsistencies in the relationship between teaching and outcomes between countries. For classroom observations, teaching practices were significantly associated with achievement gains only in one country when students' previous knowledge was controlled for, while the relationship to interest in mathematics and self-efficacy varied greatly between teaching-quality dimensions and countries (OECD, 2020). Effects on student outcomes of student-perceived teaching quality were only apparent for some dimensions of teaching quality, and even those were only notable in a few countries (Herbert et al., 2022).

The findings thus suggest that any association between teaching and student outcomes may reflect students' previous knowledge rather than the effects of teaching quality and that country should be considered when measuring teaching quality as it

seems to work differently for different dimensions in different educational systems (Research Question 1). In these two TALIS video publications, the country context is defined as including aspects of culture and educational policy and thus acknowledged as a primary factor in shaping the relationship between teaching and student outcomes. Still, Type 1 and Type 3 studies such as PISA, TIMSS, and TALIS carry an implicit assumption that teaching quality is universal as it is measured the same way, while the reviewed studies suggest that the way teaching quality affects learning is not necessarily universal. Little attention is paid in TER to how cultural or national characteristics might contribute to such variable results (Research Question 2).

Discussion

Explaining inconsistent and small effects in TER: the contribution of context

Our analysis of the literature first focused on the question of how teaching quality is related to selected context categories (Research Question 1). For each of the three categories, the literature review indicates that context has a significant impact on teaching quality in most studies. Understanding the concrete context and how it is treated in studies might therefore help to explain inconsistencies between studies. Our analysis does not allow inferences on whether larger effects would be found if context was considered more carefully in research design. To answer this question would require experimental studies that directly compare different treatments of context under controlled conditions.

Our analysis then focused on explicit and implicit conceptual assumptions about the relationship between context and teaching quality in empirical studies (Research Question 2). In all three context categories, many studies assumed that teaching quality is a universal construct. Therefore, teaching quality was conceptualized and measured in the same way even when classroom composition, learning content, and country differed. Although several studies point to quite big empirical differences resulting from different contexts, the assumption in TER remains that there are universal constructs that can be measured in the same way regardless of context. Our findings strongly suggest that future theoretical and empirical research on teaching quality must take a much more critical view of this entrenched premise.

Before continuing with this discussion, it is worth considering whether our choice of context categories and highlighted studies shaped our findings. We would argue that we chose to conduct our review within three context categories that encompass a large variety of the context variables found in the literature, and our literature review included a sizeable number of studies. These two factors allowed us to distinguish significant patterns that suggest that the use of context in TER needs to be reconsidered.

Revisiting the role of context in TER

Given our finding that context categories significantly shape results in TER, we believe that there are two ways of improving how the field approaches context. One is to continue to improve the treatment of context within the current approaches of TER. The other involves a fundamental shift, integrating context variables and teaching quality.

The main argument for the first is that while context categories and teaching quality are related, they can still be clearly empirically separated. The most promising way forward would be to ensure more careful statistical controls of context variables, ensuring that they do not significantly influence study outcomes. However, it is not clear if this is possible when considering teaching as interactions between teachers, students, and content, all embedded in an environment (D. K. Cohen et al., 2003).

The more radical option, which we favor, is that TER needs conceptualizations and measurements of teaching quality that are more contextualized (for a similar argument, see Bell & Gitomer, 2023). This argument can be illustrated by considering country (or culture) in teaching quality. From current cross-cultural research on teaching effectiveness, we know about patterns of teaching (Grant et al., 2013; Stigler & Hiebert, 1999), about how teaching and student outcomes are related, and how they often differ between countries (e.g., OECD, 2020). We also know that the more culturally different countries are, the less likely it is that teaching-quality measures are invariant (e.g., Fischer et al., 2019; Scherer et al., 2016), although there are some exceptions (see Maulana et al., 2021). While measurement-invariance studies may help establish which aspects of established constructs are comparable across countries, they do not help to explain country-specific aspects of teaching quality, and, as noted, there is little evidence that we can use the same conceptualization and instrument to measure teaching quality in multiple countries. We would therefore argue that it is time to start viewing teaching quality as culturally dependent and examine in greater depth how and why the relationships between teaching and student outcomes differ between countries. Such considerations are largely missing from TER literature (Herbert et al., 2022).

The need for more contextualized conceptualizations and measurements of teaching quality in TER is even clearer when looking at the other two categories investigated in this paper. If context is defined as something external to the unit of analysis and teaching is conceptualized as a social system of the interactions between teachers and students around the content, then neither content nor student behavior, which are inextricably linked to classroom composition, should be treated as context by TER but rather as essential, defining, aspects of teaching and its quality. They should therefore not be omitted when conceptualizing and conducting empirical studies of teaching quality by either not including these variables in the analyses or by treating them as variables external to teaching that can be controlled for. If they are integral aspects of teaching, controlling for them would mean that valid parts of the variance in teaching quality are excluded, which in turn may be part of the explanation of small to negligible effects of teaching quality on student outcomes.

Towards improved concepts of addressing context in TER

Aiming for an adequate representation of the complexity of teaching quality, and of the specific context in which teaching occurs, we face a major challenge: When everything varies and is different, how can we compare studies and accumulate knowledge? In our view, we should not abandon the idea of cumulative research but work harder to ensure our results can be linked through closer collaboration. The idea would not be to replicate generalized findings but to contribute pieces to a large puzzle. This requires

(a) more theoretical work and (b) a further development of existing empirical approaches for dealing with context categories when investigating teaching quality.

Advancing our theoretical understanding of teaching quality

On a theoretical level, we should attend more closely to the specifics of “who teaches what to whom” in order to be in a better position to identify the desired effects of teaching quality on student outcomes (see also Scheerens, 2016), instead of consigning all of these considerations to “context”. To further incorporate context into our work, we suggest developing theories of teaching quality that are broad enough to capture differences in content or composition (see also Biddle & Anderson, 1986) and using a common language and structure to describe these constructs. Theories constructed in this way would allow us to discuss teaching quality beyond the specific complexities of any study. The theories should therefore be broad enough to provide an umbrella that covers teaching in all of its variety (Bell & Gitomer, 2023). At the same time, we need to enhance these theories with more detailed specifications for different settings, content, students, and so forth. This involves acknowledging that teaching quality can be different for each student and that content and societies shape our understanding of what constitutes high-quality teaching.

Advancing empirical approaches for investigating teaching quality

We believe that it is time to be more coherent about how we apply our theoretical considerations to empirical investigations of teaching quality. This will increase the likelihood of finding more robust effects in the future.

The first step involves the operationalization of teaching quality. We should strive to adapt our existing research instruments to measure what we are trying to measure, such as the specifics of classroom management in third-grade swimming instruction, instead of producing a huge number of instruments that either do not take into account the context in which teaching occurs or are developed for very specific contexts and are not sufficiently related to each other. This means developing suitable measurement tools in cooperation with researchers who specialize in subject-specific learning or are knowledgeable about the situation and environment in which the learning takes place. We believe that most modifications of existing instruments for issues related to context need to be made with respect to the observable indicator level and the specific items, while we would expect that fewer revisions would be required on the level of (sub)dimensions (see also Praetorius et al., 2020). We could therefore start by investigating which observable indicators or items in existing instruments have (a) a similar meaning across different contexts, (b) a different meaning (they might be more or less important for the construct of interest up to being irrelevant for it), and (c) which indicators are relevant but have been omitted by researchers. In a next step, instruments could then be enhanced and adapted to context specifics as needed.

Further, we should carefully check the coherence of our theoretical arguments and empirical methods. In our analysis we found that the statistical models used in the studies we identified varied a great deal and sometimes did not support the arguments made in the paper. Moderation effects, for example, are always based on the assumption that teaching quality and the context variable(s) can be separated. However, in the reviewed studies assumptions like these were hardly mentioned, let alone discussed. In

addition, if we are to shift our research focus from “What works?” to “How does it work?”, and thus move away from linking teaching characteristics to student outcomes in order to statistically demonstrate that teaching is germane for student outcomes, and instead investigate more closely *how* teaching shapes learning, the specific details of the classrooms being studied have to be more carefully considered. One way to achieve this would be to combine quantitative and qualitative research approaches more systematically than has been done in TER to date.

Furthermore, we should take a more critical and careful approach to improving the generalizability of our findings, rather than placing so much emphasis on confirming hypotheses (see also Krammer, 2023). This means being more upfront about the challenges of a study, not burying this information in the limitations section. Answering the following questions in our papers might be productive: What does context mean for my study? Which of the aspects that I am investigating are part of the system, and which are not? What findings do I want to generalize? Do I have sufficient validity evidence for why this is justified? If this is not the case, how can I gather further evidence on the extent to which this is justified for the claims made in my study? The insights we gain from such analyses must then be fed back into the models and theories we work with (Renkl, 2022).

Conclusion

Our key suggestion is not to erase the term *context* from research on teaching quality but to ensure that it is used more carefully and consistently than it has been in the past. This includes checking whether the variables can actually be treated as context or describe the setting in which teaching takes place and are thus an integral part of the phenomenon we want to study. As our discussions of content and classroom composition have shown, it also involves expanding the conceptualizations of teaching quality and developing measurement tools that are sensitive to these elements. If this is not possible or useful for a study, it at least needs to be made explicit what omitting an element of teaching quality implies for the study and the interpretation of its findings. Furthermore, we would argue that statistically controlling for context categories or combining them into meta-analyses will not move our field forward in terms of revealing the elusive relationships between teaching quality and student outcomes. This does not mean that meta-analyses should be abandoned, but that it might be more useful to shift our attention. In order to focus on these effects, we need to widen our theoretical understanding of teaching to include all aspects of the instructional triangle, to be more explicit about our underlying assumptions concerning generalizability, and to make sure our designs and research methods align with our theoretical assumptions.

Note

1. In the literature, different terms such as environment, surrounding, ecology, and setting, are used for what we call context in this paper.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Appendix 1. Mentions of “context” in chapters of *Theorizing Teaching* (Praetorius & Charalambous, 2023a).

Classification category	Concrete mentioning in the chapter	Reference in the book
Individual contexts	Student characteristics	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 61)
	Student background characteristics	Kyriakides et al. (2023, p. 148)
	Age	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Grade level	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, pp. 61, 86)
	Learning trajectories	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
Classroom contexts	Personal contexts	Hill & Lampert (2023, pp. vi, viii)
	Subject matter	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 61)
	Classroom task	Hiebert & Stigler (2023, p. 47)
	Student populations	Hiebert & Stigler (2023, p. 47)
	Classroom experiences	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Instructional context(s)	Herbst & Chazan (2023, p. 201)
	Resources	Schoenfeld (2023, p. 183)
	Situational context	Schoenfeld (2023, p. 174)
School contexts	Independent variables affecting opportunities and/or use, but sometimes also as moderator variables that moderate the associations between opportunity and use	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 81)
	School contexts	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 61)
	School types	Scheerens (2023, p. 103)
Institutional contexts	School contexts	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Institutional position	Herbst & Chazan (2023, p. 199)

(Continued)

Continued.

Classification category	Concrete mentioning in the chapter	Reference in the book
Cultural and socio-economic contexts	Institutional context(s)	Herbst & Chazan (2023, pp. 199, 213)
	Formal education	Biesta (2023, pp. 262–263)
	Educational context(s)	Biesta (2023, pp. 262–263) Praetorius & Charalambous (2023c, p. 286)
	Countries	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Country context	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 81)
	Language areas	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Social groups	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Curriculum	Scheerens (2023, p. 103)
	Family or community context	Biesta (2023, p. 263)
	Local context	Scheerens (2023, p. 103)
Non-specific use	Social context(s)	Cai et al. (2023, p. 245) Cai et al. (2023, pp. 245, 232) Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 87) Hill & Lampert (2023, p. viii)
	Social-historical contexts	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 86)
	Political context	Hill & Lampert (2023, p. viii)
	Sociopolitical contexts	Praetorius & Charalambous (2023b, p. 18)
	Cultural context	Cai et al. (2023, p. 236)
	Sociotechnical factors	Herbst & Chazan (2023, p. 199)
	Racial contexts	Hill & Lampert (2023, p. viii)
	Ethnic contexts	Hill & Lampert (2023, p. viii)
	Economic contexts	Hill & Lampert (2023, p. viii)
	Theories of teaching that are very narrowly focused on a particular teaching phenomenon in a specific context	Cai et al. (2023, p. 237)
Theory for teaching provides explanatory power (possibly specific to the context)	Cai et al. (2023, p. 243)	
Other contextual variables	Hiebert & Stigler (2023, p. 47)	
Across a wide variety of contexts and content	Hiebert & Stigler (2023, pp. 36–37)	
The effect of contextual factors on student outcomes	Kyriakides et al. (2023, p. 133)	
The role of context ... and content matter ... further received increasing attention	Vieluf & Klieme (2023, p. 63)	
... what would you have to know about that person, and the context, in order to explain/predict that person's decision making?	Schoenfeld (2023, pp. 161–162)	

Appendix 2. References identified in the literature review.

References classroom composition

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